

ON RUSSELL'S PUZZLE 'THE PRESENT KING OF FRANCE IS NOT BALD'

ABSTRACT. Russell poses as a puzzle to solve the truth or falsehood of the expression 'The present King of France is not bald' in relation to the law of excluded middle. He offers his proposal for a solution with a theory of denotation, characterized by an excessive complication, as himself asserts. We argue that there is a simpler natural logical way out, based on the strict analysis of the contradictories and contraries of a proposition, and its exclusive disjunctions.

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According to Bertrand Russell, theories like Frege's about denotation are wrong, and hence he seeks to develop an alternative proposal, which allows solving a set of puzzles, among which he proposes the following:

By the law of excluded middle, either 'A is B' or 'A is not B' must be true. Hence either 'the present King of France is bald' or 'the present King of France is not bald' must be true. Yet if we enumerated the things that are bald, and then the things that are not bald, we should not find the present King of France in either list. (Russell 1905, p. 485)

However, after exposing his theory, himself acknowledges:

Of the many other consequences of the view I have been advocating, I will say nothing. I will only beg the reader not to make up his mind against the view - as he might be tempted to do, on account of its apparently excessive complication- until he has attempted to construct a theory of his own on the subject of denotation. This attempt, I believe, will convince him that, whatever the true theory may be, it cannot have such a simplicity as one might have expected beforehand. (Russell 1905, p. 493)

Without talking globally about Russell's or Frege's theory of denotation, we consider that at least as far as the puzzle of 'The present King of France' is concerned, a simpler and more logically natural analysis than Russell's can be carried out, resorting to the most basic premises of logic, emphasizing the characteristics of formal denial and the disjunction in the case of the law of excluded middle.

Russell argues that the statement 'The present King of France is bald' has meaning and 'is certainly false' (Russell 1905, p. 490). Argument with which we agree. There are, on the other side, positions such as that of Strawson (Strawson 1950), who considers that such a statement is neither true nor false. But we accept as convincing Russell's response to this, refuting Strawson, since Strawson assumes that Russell is saying something more abstract than what the latter actually raises: he takes the phrase put forward by Russell as

if to say (A): "The king of France is bald" (although Strawson uses the equivalent expression "The king of France is wise"), ignoring the word "present", instead of (B): "The *present* king of France is bald".

Now, Strawson differentiates between a sentence and the use of a sentence. For him, a sentence is not true or false, while the use of that sentence is. He puts (A) as an example of what he calls a sentence. And he says:

"The two persons who uttered the sentence, one during the reign of Louis XV and the other during the reign of Louis XIV, each made a different use of the same sentence" [Strawson 1950, p. 325].

Use made by each person that is true or false. He regards (B) also as a sentence, and not as the use of a sentence, and affirms:

"We are apt to fancy we are talking about sentences and expressions when we are talking about the uses of sentences and expressions. This is what Russell does" [Ibid, p. 327].

But that is not what Russell does: If Russell said (A) Strawson would be correct on this point. But Russell in fact says (B), as he makes clear in his reply (Russell 1957). Where he points out that (B) when uttered in 1905 (date of publication of his article "On Denotation") was the same as saying "The King of France in 1905 is bald".

Actually, according to Strawson's own terminology, (B) is a different use of the same sentence, referring to the year 1905, and is not the more abstract utterance (A). Therefore, according to his criteria, plus the clarification just highlighted, (B) is the use of a sentence that is true or false. This use is what Russell analyzes.

Regarding other aspects covered in Strawson's article, we will not stop in this paper. Here we focus on figuring out what happens after accepting that the statement (B) is significant (makes sense), and false when contrasted with the facts, as Russell does (or even by supposing its falsity as a mere initial hypothesis). Thus, from such a starting point, the contradictory statement 'The present King of France is not bald' would have to be true, by the principle of excluded middle. But, by another argument, 'The current King of France is not bald' can be both true and false, Russell says; it

is false if it means 'There is an entity which is now King of France and is not bald', but is true if it means 'It is false that there is an entity which is now King of France and is bald'. (Russell 1905, p. 490)

If false, the expression 'The King of France' has a 'primary occurrence'. If true, it has a 'secondary occurrence' (Russell, *ibid.*).

Let us ponder:

1. We argue that once it is accepted that 'The present King of France is bald' is false, the statement 'The present King of France is not bald' can only be logically true, because it is contradictory to a false proposition; and it is not true sometimes and sometimes false, depending on the case. The latter is only applicable to the possible contrary opposites that can, as something additional and subsequent, specify the contradictory. The puzzle can be solved by a natural logic application of denial and disjunction. And you don't need for this a theory of denotation, although it may be required for other aspects.

Furthermore, we start from the basics: as Aristotle points out,

Things are said to be opposed to one another in four ways: as relatives or as contraries or as privation and possession or as affirmation and negation. (Aristotle 2002, Categories 10 11^b17)

By the plain negation, we are talking about the contradictory one: $\neg A$ is contradictory to A , being its strict denial. As it is known, by the principle of excluded middle, $\neg A$ is always only one. There cannot be two strict denials of A different from each other [see Aristotle, *ibid.*].

On the other hand, the contraries go beyond mere negation, they affirm something additional with respect to what is denied (except in the special case when there is only one opposite, when this strictly coincides with the contradictory one). They are the contradictory + something: for example, "x is not white" + "it is blue".

In that sense, we call n-opposites the number of opposites that correspond to a sentence, be they the contrary opposed or the contradictories opposed. If the only opposed B of A is exactly the same contradictory $\neg A$, then to B corresponds the designation of 1-opposite; and there are no intermediate options: $B \equiv \neg A$. For example, in $A =$ 'x is an even natural number', the contradictory $\neg A$ is 'x is not an even natural number'; and B is the one and only one opposite.

In $A =$ 'The color of x is white', the contradictory $\neg A$ is, exclusively, 'The color of x is not white'. And to B corresponds a large number of contraries n-opposites, for example 'black', 'blue', 'red', 'green', etc. Of which only one can be true if A is false, for example, 'The color of x is black' (again, by the application of the principle of excluded middle, which here would discard any non-black color).

2. As is well known, the principle of excluded middle applies to strict denial, to contradictory propositions to each other, and not to contraries n-opposite ones that go beyond mere denial; applies to 'Either the color is white or the color is not white'; but not to 'Either the color is white or the color is black'. For black and white can be false at the same time.

Now, logically speaking, does the other option mentioned by Russell exist? Does 'The present King of France is not bald' is true or false according to primary or secondary occurrence? A logical fallacy that can appear is the confusion between the strict contradictory opposite and the contrary opposites of an expression.

Now well,

(1) 'The present King of France is bald',
accepted as false, either by *contrast* with the facts, as Russell does, or by mere *assumption*, has as contradictory, as mere denial, and not as a contrary,

(2) 'The present King of France is not bald',
which must be therefore true, by the principle of excluded middle.

From 'The present King of France is not bald' two possible contraries can be stated. But those two opposites are two different expressions regarding the contradictory one. That is, none of these opposites means exactly the same thing as that proposition, which is only a negation of (1), like "x is not white" does not mean exactly the same as "x is blue". Those opposites can be exposed like Russell rethinks them (nevertheless he does not discern them as contraries, but as two forms that express simply the contradictory one, depending on the case):

Either

(3) 'It is false that there is an entity which is now King of France and is bald', which is true.

Or

(4) 'There is an entity which is now King of France and is not bald', which is false.

As a result of all this, the law of excluded middle cannot be applied to sentence (1) as contradictory regarding the opposites (3) or (4), which are more than the mere negation of (1), but only regarding sentence (2), its strict denial. The problem comes down to considering false both, (1) and its opposite contrary (4) (as in 'x is white' against 'x is black' to consider false both when for example x is red).

3. 'The present King of France is not bald', as a contradictory expression of 'The present King of France is bald', is not specific, not univocal (like all contradictory expressions, except on those occasions where there is only one opposite), because it implies two possibilities as opposites: (3) or (4). As also is not univocal, for example, 'The color is not white' which implies many opposing possibilities.

It should be highlighted, then, that any denial, as long as it is a contradictory statement that additionally involves more than one possible n-opposition, is *ambiguous*; but ambiguous (*sense-1*) only in such a way that it is not univocal; but not in the *sense-2* of not having a well-determined meaning ('The color is not blue' has an undeniable meaning, not ambiguous according to sense-2, but it does not univocally specify (sense-1) the true color that is the case).

In fact, expression (2) is ambiguous (not specific) with respect to (3) and (4) (the contrary opposites), but not to (1), being the clear, significant, and only negation of the latter. In numerical base 3, there are only the figures 0, 1, and 2. For any number's digit, happens either A) the digit is 0, or B) the digit is not 0. If B occurs, then there are two new empirical options: either the figure is 1 or it is 2. B is not ambiguous in the sense-2 of equivocal, misleading, or unclear. It is clear and univocal concerning A. It is ambiguous only in the 1-sense of non-specific for which of the contraries is the case.

We don't need to specify the opposites of B to make a well-defined meaning. The law of the excluded middle is preserved just by taking account of B, without specifying the opposites that are the case. Without the need to identify, for example, primary or secondary occurrences. Like in 'The number is 0 or the number is not 0' there is no ambiguity of meaning and the law is preserved; without specifying an opposite ('The number is 1' or 'The number is 2').

4. In addition, it should be emphasized that the contradiction entails, where it corresponds to more than one possible n-opposite, a series of *exclusive disjunctions* (XOR in Boolean terminology: either x is A or x is B, but not both at the same time) between each contrary. And it is sufficient the truth of one of them so that the contradictory that entails such disjunctions is also true. Example: In 'The color is white' the contradictory 'The color is not white' implies the opposites of white in the color's universe: black XOR blue XOR red XOR green, etc. It is enough that a member of the disjunction, for example the opposite "black", be true for the disjunction to be true, and therefore it is *confirmed* that the contradictory one is *true*.

This also applies to the case of baldness dealt with by Russell. Which is not a special instance essentially different from the other cases whose examples we have put in this article. Thus, the contradictory $\neg A$ = 'The present King of France is not bald' gives rise to the mentioned two additional opposite possibilities, diverse to the mere denial, other than this contradictory: (3) (which is true) XOR (4) (which is false).

And so, the disjunction is true. That is, it confirms that the contradictory from which the statements in disjunction derive is true.

Russell says 'The present King of France is not bald' can be both false and true, according to primary and secondary occurrences. But from what we have already seen, it can actually only be true, by the principle of the excluded middle; and this truth can be

confirmed because one of the possible opposites, contraries, in disjunction, raised from such an expression, being true, also gives to that statement a value of truth.

The ones he calls primary and secondary *occurrences* are only, actually, the specific dichotomies, contraries, 2-opposites (contradictory + something), of the statement $A =$ 'The present King of France is bald', encompassed as exclusive disjunctions entailed by the contradictory $\neg A =$ 'The present King of France is not bald'. Hence, $\neg A \neq$ (3) and $\neg A \neq$ (4). Viz. $\neg A$ doesn't mean (3) nor (4). That is, (3) and (4) do not perform their occurrence in the contradictory (2), as Russell believes, but in the contraries.

Reinforcing this argument, it must be considered that the contrary of an expression always logically entails its contradictory, for example, with respect to the proposition "x is white", the proposition "x is blue" necessarily implies the expression "x is not white". But, not vice versa, the contradictory of an expression does not necessarily entail some contrary, when there is more than one; the expression "x is not white" does not necessarily entail the proposition "x is blue"; there is no double implication, that is, the 'if and only if', and therefore there can be no logical identity neither in the sense nor in the reference between both sentences, it does not happen that one statement is the same as the other as its mere internal occurrence.

Thus, for proposition (1) put forward by Russell, proposition (3), or proposition (4), necessarily entails, each one for its part, the expression (2). But, conversely, the expression (2) does not necessarily entail proposition (3) or (4); the 'if and only if' does not occur, and therefore there is no logical identity between (2) and (3) or (2) and (4).

Then, the primary occurrences, or the secondary occurrence, are not meanings internal to the contradictory, but external to it. By arriving at the utterance of these occurrences in the contraries, we have abandoned the contradictory expression from which we started.

Primary or secondary occurrences are new sentences with a different logical relationship regarding (1) than the relationship of (2) with (1), and they occur only if we *want* to call primary occurrences to the contraries that make the sentence false, and secondary occurrence the contrary that makes the sentence true. But it is up to us not to confuse the contradictory one with the contraries.

In this sense, the primary or the secondary occurrences can only be empirical: their truth, or how many there are, does not depend more than on the facts (for example, if the color is black XOR not black, or if there is a certain number of not black options. Or, with only two options, if there is an entity that is now king of France and is not bald XOR there is not an entity that is now king of France and is not bald) and not on a formal logical question such as, for example, on the principle of the excluded middle. This is clearer when there are more than two possible opposed options. In this case, all possible options that do not happen may be called 'secondary occurrences', after empirically determining which one is the opposite taking place in the facts, which may be called the 'primary occurrence'.

Once we establish by experience, or even assume as a premise, that 'The present King of France is bald' is false, the truth or falsehood of his plain denial no longer depends on a theory of denotation or reference, and we don't need, at that point, to 'enumerate the things that are bald, and then the things that are not bald' to find, or 'not find the present King of France in either list' (Russell 1905, p. 485).

Logical analysis based rigorously on the excluded middle is necessary and sufficient. When from the contradictory an additional exclusive disjunction in the opposites (or more) is possible, the empirical selection of the opposite option that occurs suffices; enumerating, only until that moment, those things that exist XOR the things that don't exist, and, if they exist, those that are bald and those that aren't.

Compare what Kant names polytomy:

A division into two members is called dichotomy; but if it has more than two members, it is called polytomy. ... Polytomy cannot be taught in logic, for it involves cognition of the object. Dichotomy requires only the principle of contradiction, however, without being acquainted, as to content, with the concept one wants to divide. (Kant, Immanuel 1992, section 113)

(1) and its contradictory (2) form a dichotomy. (1) and their contraries (3) and (4) form a three-member polytomy.

In short, statement (2) is neither proposition (3) nor proposition (4). The development of the different occurrences turns the expression (2) into the new sentences (3) and (4), which are different from it. It is not the same expression with different meanings. Like for example "x is not white" does not mean "x is blue", nor does "x is black". Either of these last two meanings corresponds to a later and different proposition.

In order to save the validity of the principle of excluded middle in the puzzle raised by Russell, it is not necessary to rethink the contradictory as a logical expression without grammatical subject, nor to appeal to different internal occurrences into the same contradictory judgment, with which the logical analysis is difficult; it is sufficient to adequately distinguish the contradictory from the contraries.

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